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**THE ODER-VISTULA-DNIESTER CANAL
- THE INFRASTRUCTURAL LEGACY OF THE HABSBURG EMPIRE**

KAROL WITKOWSKI

Institute of Geography and Spatial Organization, Polish Academy of Sciences,

Św. Jana St. 22, 31-018 Krakow, Poland

witkowski@zg.pan.krakow.pl

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Karol-Witkowski-2>

KONRAD MEUS

Institute of History and Archival Studies, University of the National Education Commission,

Podchorążych St. 2, 30-084 Krakow, Poland

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ABSTRACT

At the turn of the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, France and Prussia had a developed network of inland shipping channels. At that time, Austria-Hungary was mainly developing railway connections. Nevertheless, in 1901 the Habsburg Empire decided to build a network of canals connecting the Danube, Elbe, Oder, Vistula, and Dniester. The new investment was to be carried out primarily near the northern borders of the Empire. The Canal Act was an element of the political game of the Austrians, who sought the votes of Bohemian and Galician deputies in support of railway investments. The act was also used as an element of propaganda about the unity of the crown countries of the Empire. The huge planned costs of building canals and regulating rivers, the distant prospect of return on investment, and strong competition from the railways meant that the government in Vienna withheld the implementation of the act for many years. Thanks to the great stubbornness of representatives of the Galician authorities and the support of industry organizations, the construction of the canal connecting the Oder and the Vistula began in 1911. On the occasion of the construction of the canal near Zator, the construction of hydrotechnical structures in Krakow which were to make possible water transport services in the future was compelled. World War I interrupted work on the canal. During the period of the Second Republic of Poland, the concept of the course of the canal was changed several times. In 1939, the work was again interrupted by the war. In the 1950s, the structures built during the construction of the Oder-Vistula canal were incorporated into the short lateral canal of the Vistula. What remained after the great idea of making Galicia navigable was irretrievably destroyed by the regulation of the rivers, and Krakow boulevards which were not adapted to hydrological conditions. The remnants of the canal construction project in the Habsburg Empire constitute its infrastructural legacy.

KEY WORDS: Habsburg Empire, Galicia, shipping canal, waterway, infrastructural legacy

INTRODUCTION

The network of shipping canals of the Habsburg Empire, which was to include the Galician Canal, was intended to revolutionise twentieth-century transport and become a driving force for the economies of the crown countries and the entire state. In the nineteenth century, when France and Prussia already had a dense network of waterways, the Austro-Hungarian Empire all the time discussing the construction of artificial canals. The design of the new waterway network was in line with the geopolitics of the Habsburgs aiming at the unification of Central Europe.¹ The construction of canals that could connect the network of waterways from Western Europe with the Black Sea basin was also treated very seriously in Prussia and Russia.² In Vienna itself, in the long-term economic plans, it was assumed that the left-bank part of the capital would develop at the confluence of the Danube with an artificial canal to the Elbe and the Oder.³ In Bohemia and Galicia, industrialists and ordinary citizens, who had daily contact with river rafting, saw inland navigation as an opening to the wide and absorptive market of Austria and Western Europe. On the other hand, opponents of the development of water transport believed that digging canals was unnecessary and that the economy should be based on modern rail transport. The opposition was joined by the owners of large farms, who feared that groundwater would be drained by artificial canals.⁴ The discussion of Imperial transportation policy was further fuelled by the enormous cost of construction and differing estimates of when it would yield a return on investment. The investment required not only digging new canals, but adapting the natural network of waterways to supply the canal with water.⁵ Analysing individual voices in the discussion on the waterway network in the Empire,

¹ J. Janáč, *European coasts of Bohemia, negotiating the Danube-Oder-Elbe Canal in a troubled twentieth century*, Amsterdam, 2012.

² S. Turczynowicz, T. Tillinger, *The transeuropean waterway through Poland: by way of Polesie – its natural gate – and the necessity of draining that territory*, Warszawa, 1925.

³ O. Veichtlbauer, Port of Vienna: infrastructures and war on the Danube River in Vienna, 1850–1950, in: M. Landry, P. Kupper and V. Winiwarter (Eds), *Austrian Environmental History*, New Orleans, 2018, 73–102.

⁴ A. Kunz, The Performance of Inland Navigation in Germany, 1835-1935, in: A. Kunz and J. Armstrong (Eds), *Inland navigation and Economic Development in Nineteenth-Century Europe*, Mainz, 1995, 47–78.

⁵ R. Ingarden, *Rzeki i kanały żeglowne w b. trzech zaborach i znaczenie ich gospodarcze dla Polski*, Kraków, 1922.

the question arises why, with so many doubts, the decision to build a waterway network was finally made? Why were the most advanced works carried out in Galicia, which, being a peripheral country, remained underinvested throughout the nineteenth century? What impact did the unfinished construction of the Galician Canal have on the society, economy, and natural environment of Galicia?

In order to answer these questions, it was traced the fate of the Galician Canal against the background of the development of the water transport of the Habsburg Empire. In order to fully understand the relationship between man and the environment, it was necessary to know the causes and effects of legal, administrative, economic, social, and natural processes. Special attention was paid to the feedback between the examined elements. Imperial, supra-regional threads were intertwined with the microhistory of Galicia and its cities. This approach made it possible to capture the real impact of grassroots activities on the decisions made in Vienna. In addition, it was possible to indicate the effects, especially natural and infrastructural, of the construction of the Galician Canal, which are visible to this day. According to Wohl, understanding the root causes of permanent changes in the natural environment is essential to identifying 'legacies'.⁶ And only after such identification can we determine the beginning and scale of anthropopressure, as well as measures to return to the path of sustainable development. In this perspective, the Galician Canal is not only a great historical infrastructural project, but also an undertaking that led to the creation of fluvial anthropospheres that irreversibly changed the character of the Carpathian valleys.

⁶ E. Wohl, Forgotten legacies: Understanding and mitigating historical human alterations of river corridors, *Water Resources Research* 55 (2019) 5181–5201.

THE WATERWAY NETWORK OF THE HABSBURG EMPIRE

On the watercourses of the Habsburg Empire, the transport was organized as sailing or rafting. Sailing made it possible for ships to upstream and downstream. Owing to the large transport capacity, ship traffic was recorded, and so were navigable sections of rivers and artificial canals. Floatable reaches of rivers made it possible for rafts to move with the stream, and in addition only under favourable flow conditions. For this reason, rafting could take place over a shorter or longer distance depending on the season. Owing to these difficulties, rafting on most rivers was limited to the transport of unprocessed timber. Goods were usually registered only after entering the navigable sections where customs chambers existed. It was estimated that in all the crown lands of Austria, a total of about 3,900 km of river reaches were used for rafting, which accounted for 59% of all waterways in this part of the Empire.⁷

In the Austro-Hungarian monarchy at the end of the nineteenth century, over 7,648 km of waterways were used for navigation (Fig. 1, Tab. 1). The shipping routes of the time were divided into 4 classes: artificial canals and natural rivers accessible to steamboats or rowing ships.⁸ The category of natural rivers included only large rivers in the Empire, the channel pattern of which, and flow conditions, allowed navigation for most of the year. The lack of regulatory works resulted in interrupting the continuity of navigation on many rivers, e.g. the Drava was not navigable between the border of Carinthia and Styria and Maribor.

The main waterway of the Habsburg Empire was the Danube. In the nineteenth century, it was primarily used to transport timber harvested in Lower and Upper Austria. In the early 1830s, about 250,000 tonnes of firewood and construction wood, food, and other goods were

⁷ T. Pilat, *Podręcznik statystyki Galicyi, tom 7, część 2*, Lwów, 1904, 214–215. A unique type of floatable canal, which cannot be classified as a waterway, was the Schwarzenbergsche Schwemmkanal in the Bohemian and Austrian Šumava, the construction of which began in 1789. The canal was built on the estate of Joseph II, Prince Schwarzenberg. After many extensions, the canal reached a length of 51.9 km. This canal was a gutter (2.2–2.8 m wide and 0.8 m deep), which was used to float tree trunks without nailing them into rafts. Man did not take part in the transport, but was supposed to prevent congestion. E. Fritsch, *Der Schwarzenberg-Schwemmkanal im Wandel der Zeit. Mitteilungen des Landesvereins für Höhlenkunde in Oberösterreich* 39, 1 (1993) 43–74.

⁸ Map Die Schifffahrtsstrassen in Österreich-Ungarn in: *Brockhaus' Konversations-Lexikon, edition 14, reprint 3, volume 12 Moria-Pes*, Leipzig, Berlin, Vienna, 1903, 716–717.

delivered to Vienna by ships. Just before the regulation of the Danube in Vienna, in 1870, about 600,000 tonnes of goods reached the city by steamboats. Extensive river training made it possible for large ships to enter the city centre (Donaukanal) and eliminated the risk of flooding to the east of the city centre. During the construction, the location of future city parks and markets as well as industrial zones was also taken into account. The regulation freed up 260 hectares of land along the new main channel of the Danube. It was envisaged that the villages north of the main channel would develop in the future at the connection of the Danube waterway with the Danube-Oder-Elbe Canal.⁹

The Danube shipping opened the Empire to the Black Sea, which is why the Iron Gate water gap between the Southern and Serbian Carpathians was a very important place. In 1831, on the initiative of the Hungarian entrepreneur István Széchenyi, a design for the Danube canalisation was developed in a rocky water gap that was a threat to navigation. River training combined with rock blasting was completed in 1896.¹⁰

Within Austria, from Passau to Devin, there were 346 km of the Danube channel, and in Hungary, from Devin to Orşova, 960 km. Both reaches were fully navigable. Above Passau, in Germany, the Danube was navigable from Ulm (547 km), and similarly below Orşova, to its mouth opening into the Black Sea (981 km). The entire international navigable course of the Danube was a route of 2,834 km. In addition, five natural side branches were sailed, including the Moson Danube and the Szentendre Danube.

Apart from the Viennese Donaukanal, only two artificial canals were built in Austria. The Lendkanal, 4.1 km long, connected Klagenfurt with Lake Worthersee. The first canal was

⁹ G. Haidvogel, V. Winiwarter, G. Dressel, S. Gierlinger, F. Hauer, S. Hohensinner, G. Pollack, C. Spitzbart-Glasl and E. Raith, Urban waters and the development of Vienna between 1683 and 1910, *Environmental History* 23 (2018) 736.

¹⁰ C. Ardeleanu, *International trade and diplomacy at the Lower Danube: the Sulina question and the economic premises of the Crimean War (1829–1853)*, Brăila, 2014; L. Gatejel, Overcoming the Iron Gates: Austrian transport and river regulation on the Lower Danube, 1830s–1840s, *Central European History* 49, 2 (2016) 162–180.

built in 1527 to supply the city with water. After 30 years, the canal was expanded to its present size. In the eighteenth century, Klagenfurt maintained a fleet of a hundred ships that brought fish, building materials, lime, and coal.¹¹ However, from the beginning of the twentieth century, the canal was used only for tourist shipping.

According to government plans, the most important artificial canal in Austria was to be the Wiener Neustadt Canal, built in the years 1797–1803. The canal connecting the Danube with Trieste on the Adriatic was supposed to make possible the transport of coal, wood, and bricks from the southern part of the Empire. Eventually, for economic reasons, a connection between Vienna and Wiener Neustadt was built with a branch to Pötsching, near Hungarian Sopron. In the nineteenth century, freight transport on this route was taken over by the railway, and the canal itself was no longer included in the list of waterways.¹² At the end of the nineteenth century, artificial waterways in Austria accounted for a total of 2.4% of the shipping routes of the Empire.

The statistics also included ten canals in the Venetian Plain with a total length of 42.7 km. These channels included not only sections dug on land, but also routes through the lagoon. These dykes were created in Roman times and did not play role in transport.¹³

Several important artificial shipping channels functioned in Hungary, the total length of which accounted for 7.9% of Hungarian shipping routes. The oldest of them was built as a lateral channel to the natural channel of the Bega River. It started in Timosoara and ended as it flowed into the Tisza at Titel. Work began in 1777. The canal was extended until 1837. The

¹¹ T. Polley, *Klagenfurt - vom Zollfeld bis zum Wörthersee*, Wien, Hamburg, 1973, 327.

¹² L. Ažman Momirski, The Resilience of the Port Cities of Trieste, Rijeka, and Koper, *Journal of Urban History* 47, 2 (2021) 293–316.; *Brockhaus' Konversations-Lexikon, edition 14, reprint 2, volume 12 Morea – Perücke*, Leipzig, Berlin, Vienna, 1898, 716.

¹³ Map Die Schifffahrtsstrassen in Österreich-Ungarn.

Begakanal, 115 km long, was used mainly for the timber rafting, but its parameters made it possible for steamboats to navigate on it.¹⁴

The longest canal in the Habsburg Empire was the Franzenskanal (modern name: the Great Bačka Canal), which was built in the years 1793-1801. The canal started in Bezdan on the Danube and ended in Bečej on the Tisza (123 km long, 5 locks). In the years 1871-1875, the canal network was expanded, connecting the Franzenskanal directly with the Danube via the Franz-Josephskanal (modern name: the Little Bačka Canal, 69 km long). This network of canals had the greatest impact on the water transport of the Empire because it shortened the Danube route by 250 km. These canals were used primarily to transport grain from the Banat.¹⁵

The last artificial canal important from the point of view of navigation that was built in Hungary was the Sió Canal. This facility was designed to regulate the water level of Lake Balaton, which threatened the new railway line running along the southern shore of the lake. The 12-kilometre Sió Canal, financed by the railway company, opened in 1863. The canal connected Lake Balaton to the natural river Sió and was used by small transport rowing boats.¹⁶

WATERWAYS OF GALICIA

In Galicia, only the Vistula and the Dniester as well as some reaches of the Przemsza, Dunajec, San, and Bug rivers, which constituted 819 km of waterways made navigation possible. Only the Vistula, San, and Przemsza made the traffic of steamboats possible for most of the year. For this reason, the main, and practically the only important, shipping route in Galicia was the border Vistula River (nearly 300 km long) from the mouth of the Przemsza above Krakow to Zawichost, below the mouth of the San. Inland sailors used the infrastructure

¹⁴ *Brockhaus' Konversations-Lexikon, edition 14, reprint 2, volume 2 Astrachan – Bilk*, Leipzig, Berlin, Vienna, 1898, 634.

¹⁵ *Meyers Großes Konversations-Lexikon, volume 6 Faidit – Gehilfe*, Leipzig, 1907, 587; *Brockhaus' Konversations-Lexikon, edition 14, reprint 2, volume 15 Social – Türken*, Leipzig, Berlin, Vienna, 1898, 759.

¹⁶ A. Zlinszky and G. Timár, Historic maps as a data source for socio-hydrology: a case study of the Lake Balaton wetland system, Hungary, *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 17 (2013) 4594.

developed along the Vistula from the seventeenth century, which was considered the 'golden era' of water transport in Poland. This historic success was made possible mainly owing to the transport of grain.¹⁷ Since the establishment of the Kingdom of Poland under Tsarist Russia in 1815, the Vistula river below Krakow was the border between Austria and Russia. This prevented the efficient organization of Galician shipping, as the Russian side did not agree to the canalisation of the river. An expression of this border conflict was a long-term dispute over the use of the port in Sandomierz, which served local transport between the two banks of the river.¹⁸

1,307 km of unnavigable rivers were used for the periodic timber rafting, i.e. in the Vistula basin, the Soła, Skawa, Raba, Dunajec, Wisłoka, San, and Wisłok, and, in the Dniester basin, the Stryj, Świca with Sukiel, and Bystrytsia of Nadvirna and Bystrytsia of Solotvyn. On all rivers timber rafting started in the upper reaches of the river, at a place where there was a large slope of the channel and a rushing stream. Timber stored in the channels was carried away during high flows and floated to places where the river was wide enough to make possible the movement of rafts made of several interconnected tree trunks. Such rafts were loaded with wood and wicker products or pots. This primitive method made it possible to use the rivers for transport over their greater length only a few times a year. In addition, it made rafting a dangerous activity.¹⁹

At the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, the Vistula River and its major tributaries transported mainly construction timber, which constituted the largest volume, coal, lime, construction stones, and firewood, as well as a small amount of grain, salt, and iron. The largest transports at the turn of the centuries were recorded in 1906, when a total of 194,000 tonnes of

¹⁷ J. Piasecka, Budowa kanałów na ziemiach Rzeczypospolitej w świetle piśmiennictwa polskiego do połowy XIX w., *Kwartalnik Historii Nauki i Techniki* 15, 2 (1970) 297–318.

¹⁸ Akta Namiestnictwa: sprawy wodne w zachodniej Galicji przekazane DRP w Krakowie, National Archives in Krakow, 29/309/0/2/204.

¹⁹ Ingarden, *Rzeki i kanały*.

cargo were transported using 13,400 vessels (mainly rafts and scows). The volatility of the volume of transport on the Vistula and its tributaries reflects the breakdown of the Galician economy, including the famine of 1879-1880.²⁰ The drastic decrease in the volume of transport, by 58%, in the years 1906-1911, was already resulting from the taking over of freight transport by railways and the marginalisation of inland waterways (Fig. 2). Water transport on the Dniester and its main tributaries was much less developed than on the Vistula. Navigation was possible only on the Dniester River (377 km long), and only using flat-bottomed rowing ships. For this reason, the rafting of construction timber dominated in the catchment, which in the years 1892-1907 accounted for 98 to 100% of floated goods. Apart from it, trace amounts of firewood, coal, and grain were floated.²¹

The wood transported by the Dniester came mainly from the timber area concentrated around Stanisławów, a town located in the Carpathian foothills and considered the third largest in Galicia.²² Stanisławów was considered the most important Galician town to profit from Dniester shipping. It was on the initiative of entrepreneurs from Stanisławów and of the local authorities that in 1886 a company dealing with steam navigation on the Dniester was founded.²³ The importance of river transport for timber trade is evidenced by the fact that already in 1887, Karol Mikolasch, a counsellor of the Lviv Chamber of Commerce and Industry, initiated efforts to create a specialised office dealing with forest management in Stanisławów. It was to be responsible for the organization of water transport beyond the borders of the province and the state.²⁴ Tsarist Russia remained the key recipient of timber from the Stanisławów timber area. In the 1880s, the leader in timber trade with Russia was the

²⁰ R. Łubiński, *Nieurodzaj i głód w Galicyi. R. 1879-1880*, Kraków, 1880.

²¹ Pilat, *Podręcznik statystyki Galicyi*.

²² Protokół z VI posiedzenia lwowskiej Izby handlowej i przemysłowej z dnia 3 czerwca 1889, Austrian State Archives, General Administration Archive [hereafter OeStA/AVA], AT-OeStA/AVA Handel HMallg A 486, 86.

²³ Żegluga parowa na Dniestrze, *Kurjer Lwowski*, 145, 26 May 1886, 1; Żegluga na Dniestrze, *Kurjer Lwowski*, 199, 20 July 1886, 4.

²⁴ Protokół z VI posiedzenia lwowskiej Izby handlowej i przemysłowej z dnia 20 czerwca 1887, OeStA/AVA, AT-OeStA/AVA Handel HMallg A 486, 23.

‘Adlersberg Brothers’ company from Stanisławów. The company's success resulted from the fact that river scows were used for transporting goods.²⁵

Disproportions in the development of shipping and rafting in the Vistula and Dniester basins had not only economic, but also natural causes. The rivers of the Western Carpathians are characterized by much greater flow dynamics than rivers in the Eastern Carpathians, so facilitating the organization of timber floated on all the mountain tributaries of the Vistula, starting from their upper reaches. The Vistula itself, flowing through the Sandomierz Basin, on the border of Galicia, had a natural sinuous channel pattern. The bottom of the Vistula valley was wide, which made access to the river unrestricted. The Dniester, on the other hand, in its middle course flows through the Volhynian-Podolian Upland, where it formed a deep winding ravine cut by knickpoints, of which 131 were counted in 1901.²⁶

ECONOMIC AND POLITICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INLAND NAVIGATION IN THE HABSBURG EMPIRE

In the second half of the nineteenth century, the Habsburg Empire began to develop intensively the railway, which led to a strong monopolization of transport.²⁷ According to Janáč, the main reason for this situation was the very strong position of politicians associated with the Ministry of Railways.²⁸ Their actions, together with the lobbying by the owners of iron foundries, effectively hindered investment in waterways, where it was feared that they might dominate freight transport, as happened in Germany. Agricultural tycoons, fearing the loss of water resources used for irrigation, were also against the construction of waterways.²⁹ There were also voices in the public space pointing out that the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries

²⁵ K. Meus, *Izba Handlowa i Przemysłowa we Lwowie (1850-1918). Instytucja i ludzie*, Kraków, 2021, 317–318.

²⁶ A. Konopka, Ekspersi Ligi Narodów o polskich drogach wodnych, *Czasopismo Techniczne* 44, 21 (1926) 14.

²⁷ J. Martí-Henneberg, European integration and national models for railway networks (1840–2010), *Journal of Transport Geography* 26 (2013) 126–138.

²⁸ Janáč, *European coasts of Bohemia*.

²⁹ Kunz, *The Performance of Inland Navigation in Germany*.

brought the collapse of the waterway construction programme in France, which was supposed to be proof of the decreasing profitability of shipping canals throughout Europe.³⁰

Despite the unfavourable communication policy, in 1893 the Austrian government established the Department for the Research and Construction of Canals, which was to prepare the concept of building a network of inland waterways in the Austrian Empire. Already in 1894, the department's experts stated that Galicia was the country in which it was easiest to create a network of navigable rivers and canals.³¹ Despite the lack of artificial canals, Galicia had the largest share in the length of waterways among all the countries of the Austrian Empire, i.e. 31%. In addition, this share did not take into account the length of floatable rivers, which could be transformed into waterways after additional investment. The lack of investment is evidenced by the summary of the budget for the years 1843–1860, when the Viennese government spent only 3% of the funds allocated to the training of rivers throughout the Empire on Galician rivers.³²

In Galicia, various circles saw waterways as an opportunity for economic development. The canal connecting the Vistula and the Dniester was seen as an opportunity, not only to diversify the market and increase turnover in the western part of Europe, but also to increase the sale of petroleum products, spirits, construction materials, and agricultural produce. Oil extracted in the Drohobych-Boryslav Basin was of particular importance for the economic development of the region. At the beginning of the twentieth century, its price was one of the lowest in Europe. It was hoped that the launching of the canal would open Eastern Galicia to new Western European markets.³³ On the other hand, it was expected to import cheaper coal (after lowering the transport price) from the Galician coal basin concentrated in the Chrzanów

³⁰ M. Wojtkiewicz, *Śródlądowe drogi wodne na tle ewolucji transportu*, Warszawa, 1934, 437.

³¹ Janáč, *European coasts of Bohemia*.

³² A. Kędzior, *Roboty wodne i melioracyjne w Południowej Małopolsce wykonane z inicjatywy Sejmu i Wydziału Krajowego. Część I. Ogólna*, Lwów, 1928.

³³ *Sprawozdanie z czynności oraz protokoły posiedzeń plenarnych Izby handlowej i przemysłowej we Lwowie za rok 1910*, Lwów, 1910, 65; Hausner, *Odrodzenie Galicji a drogi wodne*.

and Biała poviats, and from Silesia.³⁴ On the other hand, importing cheap iron ore from the Black Sea coast to Western Galicia, together with local coal, was supposed to make the development of the domestic iron industry possible. According to Hausner, the construction of the Galician Canal through the Sandomierz Basin was also expected to contribute to the improvement of agriculture. Fertilizers, for which the demand grew every year, were to be imported through the canal, and its waters could be used to supply fish ponds. In addition, tens of thousands of local workers were to be employed in the construction of the canal.³⁵ It was estimated that, thanks to waterways, the turnover of goods would reach three million tonnes, while that recorded at the beginning of the twentieth century was less than two thousand tonnes.³⁶

At the turn of the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, advanced design work was carried out on the second railway line to Trieste - the main seaport of the Empire. This very cost-intensive investment required the consent of the Imperial Diet, in which the key votes were held by deputies from Galicia and Bohemia. In order to convince undecided politicians that they should invest in railways in the southern part of the Empire, a parallel investment was proposed in its northern part, i.e. the construction of a network of water canals.³⁷ The result of this political transaction was the adoption by Ernest von Koerber's government of the Act on the construction of waterways and the performance of river training of June 11, 1901. According to its content, in the years 1904-1923, a network of canals was to be created, connecting the Danube with the Oder, Vltava, Elbe, Vistula, and Dniester (Fig. 3A).³⁸ In the first stage, lasting until 1912, the Danube-Oder and the Oder-Vistula canals were to be built, while the Vltava and

³⁴ Kanał Wisła-Dniestr cz. III, *Kurjer Lwowski* 538, 22 November 1913, 2–3; M. Ch., Przyczynek do art. o kanale galicyjskim, *Przegląd Techniczny* 49, 22 (1911) 288–289; Z. Daszyńska-Golińska, *Rozwój i samodzielność gospodarcza ziem polskich*, Warszawa, Kraków, 1914, 153.

³⁵ Hausner, *Odrodzenie Galicji a drogi wodne*.

³⁶ W. Krzepowski, Projektowane drogi wodne w Austrii, *Przegląd Techniczny* 35 (1902) 425–429.

³⁷ A. Gerschenkron, *An Economic Spurt That Failed. Four Lectures in Austrian History*, Princeton, 1977.

³⁸ Journal of Laws of the State, No. 66, 1901. <http://alex.onb.ac.at/cgi-content/alex?aid=rgb&datum=19010004&seite=00000215>, last accessed 29 January 2023.

Elbe were to be canalised, and other works were to be designed. According to the act, the central budget of the Empire was to participate in the construction costs up to 60%. The remaining 40% was to be covered from the budget of Galicia. In connection with this, the Diet of Galicia and Lodomeria adopted its own act on the canalisation of rivers intended to flow into the Vistula-Dniester canal.³⁹ The act covered floatable rivers (in the catchment area of the Vistula, i.e. the Skawa, Raba, Dunajec, Wisłoka, San, and Wisłok; in the Dniester catchment: the Stryj, Świca and Sukiel, Bystrytsia of Nadvirna and Bystrytsia of Solotvyn) as well as the Poprad (a Dunajec tributary) and the Tanew (a San tributary), on which rafting was to develop after their canalisation. In 1907, the reaches indicated for river training were extended to include the upper courses of these rivers.⁴⁰

Despite the adoption of the act by the central government and supplementary acts by the national government, no construction work began in Galicia until 1911. The main reason for the delay in the implementation of the project was the disapproval of successive Austrian governments for this cost-intensive investment.⁴¹ Finance Minister Eugen von Bohm-Bawerek expressed a particular distaste for Prime Minister Koerber's bold and very costly development projects.⁴² Polish parliamentarians sitting in the Austrian Council of State systematically put pressure on government circles to find funding for the construction of Galician canals. Representatives of the Chamber of Commerce and Industry in Krakow also sought to start construction work as soon as possible. This issue was widely commented on in the Polish technical and daily press.⁴³ For Polish politicians, the case took on an honourable character. As noted by the outstanding Polish politician of the time, Leon Biliński, 'the Bohemians, through

³⁹ Journal of National Laws, No. 103, 1901. <http://alex.onb.ac.at/cgi-content/alex?aid=lga&datum=19010004&seite=00000321>, last accessed 29 January 2023.

⁴⁰ Journal of National Laws, No. 60, 1907. <https://alex.onb.ac.at/cgi-content/alex?aid=lga&datum=19070004&seite=00000131>, last accessed 29 January 2023.

⁴¹ L. Biliński, *Wspomnienia i dokumenty, 1846-1919*, Warszawa, 1924, 199–200.

⁴² J. Purchla, *Kraków – prowincja czy metropolia?* Kraków, 1996.

⁴³ J. Bund, *Rozwój kolejnictwa małopolskiego w okresie 80-lecia (1850-1930) działalności krakowskiej Izby Przemysłowo-Handlowej oraz przebieg starań o wykonanie ustawy Koerberowskiej o budowie dróg wodnych*, Kraków, 1930, 57.

their influence in the government, ran a significant part of the Bohemian channels'.⁴⁴ At this stage, the Bohemians managed to persuade the government to finance the regulation of the Elbe and Vltava rivers. In this matter, they successfully lobbied the owners of Bohemian mines and factories of ferrous materials who wanted to launch efficient transport. In addition, it was also expected that coal transport from Bohemia to Austria would be launched faster, the known resources of which were many times greater than in the so-called the Krakow Basin.⁴⁵

Along with the delay in the commencement of work, there were more and more voices claiming that the central government intended to abandon the construction of the canal in Galicia or even the construction of the entire canal network. These visions were fuelled by the publication of subsequent calculations indicating not only an increase in construction costs, but also emphasizing the unprofitability of the entire investment. Comments appearing in the Polish press regarding the progress in the negotiations and planning the canal resulted in an ever-increasing information clamour around the entire investment.⁴⁶

The discussion on the construction of canals gained particular momentum in the years 1910-1913. In 1911, it was because of the sluggishness in the implementation of the Galician Canal, as the Oder-Vistula-Dniester Canal was later called, that the first government of Richard Bienerth collapsed. It was also attended by Poles opting for the construction of the canal - Leon Biliński, Władysław Dulęba, Dawid Abrahamowicz, and Waclaw Zaleski.⁴⁷ Finally, in 1910, work on the preliminary designs of shipping canals was completed, the estimated cost of which increased by seven times compared to the assumptions of 1901.

⁴⁴ Biliński, *Wspomnienia i dokumenty*, 199.

⁴⁵ Kędzior, *Roboty wodne i melioracyjne w Południowej Małopolsce*, 236.

⁴⁶ H. Kozińska-Witt, '[...] gdy stary Wawel otoczą wody kanału'. Niezrealizowana droga wodna łącząca Dunaj, Wisłę i Dniestr, *Galicja. Studia i Materiały* 8 (2022) 371–376.

⁴⁷ Daszyńska-Golińska, *Rozwój i samodzielność gospodarstwa*, 153; Biliński, *Wspomnienia i dokumenty*, 201–203, *Diary: Z pamiętników moich*, volume 1, M. Bobrzyński, Jagiellonian Library in Krakow, 8105 IV, 296.

DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION OF THE CANAL IN GALICIA

The Austrian Ministry of Trade assumed, in the general schedule of canal construction, that in the first period of work, i.e. in the years 1904-1912, a canal connecting the Danube with the Oder and further with the Vistula would be built. This assumption explains why in Galicia the construction of the canal infrastructure in Krakow and the surrounding area was most often discussed, emphasizing the role and importance of the smallest details, while in the context of the whole country the focus was on the general course of the canal.⁴⁸

Social fears related to the construction of the canal in the vicinity of Krakow were widespread. They intensified especially after the catastrophic flood that hit Galicia in July 1903. At that time, after almost two weeks of rain, unregulated Galician rivers turned into a destructive element destroying everything in its path. Hundreds of towns and villages located in the basins of the upper Vistula (Western Galicia) and the Dniester (Eastern Galicia) got partly under water. Material losses were estimated at tens of millions of kronen.⁴⁹ Some people who had lost their life's possessions were forced to leave their homes and emigrate abroad, mainly to the United States. The atmosphere among Galician society was tense. Almost the whole frustration was channelled to the central government in Vienna, which had neglected investment in flood protection in Galicia for years. The inhabitants of the largest Austrian province gave vent to it during an inspection trip around Galicia by Ernest Koerber - the Austrian Prime Minister. After the flood of 1903, the central authorities began to receive objections related to the planned canal and its accompanying infrastructure. In October 1903, Krakow's local government officials, using the applicable law, made a statement regarding the activities of the Imperial and Royal Waterways Construction Directorate, in which it was

⁴⁸ O. Nadolski, Kanał żeglugi Dunaj-Odra-Wisła-Dniestr, *Przegląd Techniczny* 69 (1913) 285–288; Ingarden, *Rzeki i kanały*; M. Matakiewicz, Akcja Polskiego T-wa Politechnicznego w sprawie budowy dróg wodnych w Galicyi, *Przegląd Techniczny* 27 (1914) 363–364; Kędzior, *Roboty wodne i melioracyjne w Południowej Małopolsce*; A. Hausner, *Odrodzenie Galicji a drogi wodne*, Kraków, 1911; J. Purchla, *Matecznik Polski. Pozaekonomiczne czynniki rozwoju Krakowa w okresie autonomii galicyjskiej*, Kraków, 1992, 128–129.

⁴⁹ *Kurier Lwowski* 197, 18 July 1903, 2; *Nowa Reforma* 160, 17 July 1903, 2.

emphasized that the construction of canal infrastructure was possible only in conjunction with the regulation of the Vistula. On the other hand, the effects of river training were expected mainly to protect against flooding.⁵⁰

Cracovians not only expressed their concerns about the construction of the Galician Canal, but also proposed a number of solutions that could change the social attitude towards this great project aimed at turning Krakow into a port city. First of all, it was suggested to the designers and the investor, i.e. the Austrian Ministry of Trade, to make the Vistula river channel passable in the vicinity of the city centre during construction by building canal in the vicinity of the Pychowice district. Krakow's authorities assumed the possibility of canalising the Vistula in its reach between Krakow and Podgórze, by damming up the water with a needle dam. The side section (for the winter port) of the canal was proposed to run using the Vistula channel along the road leading towards Silesia, as far as to the suburb of Zwierzyniec. The Ministry of Trade was also requested to build two additional drainage and collector (outflow) canals one on each bank of the Vistula River in the Krakow reach of the canal. Their purpose was to collect excess rainwater and to receive sewage and waste. The necessary condition, put forward by the authorities of the city of Krakow, was the construction of boulevards. Their height was set at the level of the Vistula recorded in 1813, i.e. during the greatest flood in nineteenth-century Krakow. At the same time, the concept of launching a commercial port along the Rudawa River, which is a tributary of the Vistula, was submitted, in the area of the then village of Zwierzyniec near Krakow (since 1909 incorporated into the administrative area of Krakow). At the same time, quick (until 1904) training of the rivers flowing through the city was expected, i.e. the Rudawa and Wilga rivers. The high importance of the 'declaration' submitted in October 1903 to the Waterways Construction Directorate is evidenced by the fact that it was signed, among others, by the Mayor of Krakow Józef Friedlein, his deputy Juliusz Leo and representatives of

⁵⁰ Regulacja Wisły, Projekt kanału Wisła-Dniestr, Central Archives of Historical Records in Warsaw [hereafter AGAD], 1/310/365, 102.

the most important groups forming the then City Council: Jan Rotter - a representative of the Polish Democratic Party and a member of the National Parliament, as well as by the socialist Ignacy Daszyński, the then member of the Austrian State Council, considered one of the 'fathers of the independence' of Poland. Among the signatories of the document, representatives of the local community and representatives of economic and scientific circles of Krakow could not be missing. Therefore, the above-mentioned 'declaration' was signed by, among others, Dr Artur Benis – a popular lawyer and economist, the then secretary of the Krakow Chamber of Commerce and Industry, and Professor Tadeusz Sikorski – an engineer, specialist in water construction, working at the Agricultural College of the Jagiellonian University.⁵¹

Purchla believes that it was the plans to build shipping canals and a commercial port in Krakow that formed the basis of the city's development strategy, Greater Krakow, outlined by its then mayor, Juliusz Leo.⁵² This hypothesis is confirmed by a much earlier publication by Przeorski, who recognised the plans to build the canal as the reason for extending the borders of Krakow.⁵³ Finally, in 1906, a design was prepared for Krakow's boulevards, which exist to this very day. Both the exact location of the city port and the course of the Vistula canal were not specified, although work on the location of the port lasted until 1916.⁵⁴

The cited case of Krakow proves the problems of a social nature that accompanied the construction of the canal already at the design stage. Importantly, residents of smaller towns and even rural communes located along the Vistula also reported doubts about the investment being implemented. For example, objections were raised by Józefa Baroness Błażowska, the owner of the villages of Ryczów and Półwieś located in the Wadowice powiat, who noticed that the planned canal would separate her agricultural land from farm buildings. As a result, in 1903

⁵¹ Regulacja Wisły, Projekt kanału Wisła-Dniestr, AGAD 1/310/0/6/365, 103-104, 106, 111.

⁵² Purchla, *Matecznik Polski*, 128–129.

⁵³ T. Przeorski, *Rozszerzenie granic stol. król. M. Krakowa w latach 1909–1915*, Kraków, 1931, 211.

⁵⁴ Działalność Zarządu Miejskiego w r. 1906, *Kalendarz Krakowski Józefa Czecha na rok 1907* 76 (1907) 81; Kozińska-Witt, '[...] gdy stary Wawel otoczą wody kanału', 386.

she asked the building commission appointed by the Ministry of Trade to re-revise the route of the canal. There were many objections and comments. Some of them had substantive justification, others not. For example, the plenipotentiary of the landed estates of the town of Zator, belonging to Count August Potocki, even expected the reconstruction of insignificant field roads leading to the manor's arable land. While the claims of the Potockis in the indicated case were unfounded, the objections raised by the heads of communes were justified. And so, the head of the Łączany commune, Jan Szcząbek, demanded the construction of a passage to the arable fields, which would be cut off from the commune by the canal, and, lying between the canal and the railway line, would be deprived of access. Similar problems were reported by Zygmunt Jaworski, the administrator of the manor estates in Kossowa and Chrzastowice. In October 1903, he submitted an official protest to the powiat staroste in Wadowice, who was the representative of the government authority in the area, regarding the route of the planned waterway. Jaworski pointed out that after the construction of the canal, almost half of the manor area would be deprived of agriculture.⁵⁵

Disputes related to the route of the canal and to the expropriation of land for this investment lasted (starting from 1904) for several years.⁵⁶ It is enough to mention that as early as 1917, the Galician Governorate General drew up and made public a list of land which, after many years of negotiations, was planned to be subject to compulsory purchase for the construction of the water route in question.⁵⁷

Social controversies related to the design and implementation of the Galician Canal were considerable, and were voiced mainly by communes and private individuals who were afraid of the natural consequences of the investment. Particular interests, related to e.g. the loss of land intended for construction, often came out. It should be noted, however, that the emerging

⁵⁵ Działalność Zarządu Miejskiego, 119, 125–127.

⁵⁶ Kanał Zator - Samborek, AGAD 1/310/366, 8–26.

⁵⁷ Regulacja Wisły, Projekt kanału Wisła-Dniestr, AGAD 1/310/0/6/365, 1282–1307.

criticism was only one side of the coin. The other, outlined by representatives of economic circles in Galicia, looked optimistic. The creation of the canal in Galicia was seen as an opportunity for the development of domestic (Galician), intra-Austrian and, above all, international trade. Through the canal, it was planned to increase trade with the most important foreign partner, namely Germany.⁵⁸ Among the institutions and organizations striving for its construction, the palm of precedence was held by the chambers of commerce and industry, which at that time acted as economic self-governments. The Krakow Chamber of Commerce and Industry approached the topic enthusiastically, arguing that the new canals laid out by Galicia would make possible cheap transport of products and raw materials that were of key importance for local trade and industry, such as agricultural produce, coal, timber and wood products, spirits, and crude oil.⁵⁹ Of particular importance for the national economy was the transport of crude oil, the extraction of which in Galicia in the peak year (1909) amounted to a trifle of 207,673 tankers, each containing ten tonnes of the raw material.⁶⁰ In Krakow, it was hoped that the river trading port to be built here would place the second city of Galicia permanently on the economic map of this part of the Danubian Monarchy. It was planned that the convenient geographical location together with a well-developed railway network, after the construction of the port, would make Krakow an important transshipment point for the so-called bulk goods that would be transported on the west-east line and to the south of Europe.

Industrialists and merchants associated around the Krakow Chamber of Commerce and Industry supported the plans to build the canal, although they expressed 'regret' related, in their opinion, to the unfortunate routing of the new waterway from Zator to Krakow, because, as stated, it bypassed the 'centre of Galician industry', which for this part of Galicia was located in the Chrzanów powiat (former Kraków Basin), on the left bank of the Vistula. The battle for

⁵⁸ Meus, *Izba Handlowa i Przemysłowa*, 151, 153.

⁵⁹ Regulacja Wisły, Projekt kanału Wisła-Dniestr, AGAD 1/310/0/6/365, 108–109.

⁶⁰ Akta dotyczące się spraw..., AGAD 1/308/0/-/65, 502; R. Macyra, *Na rynku hossy i bessy. Gieldy towarowe w II Rzeczypospolitej*, Poznań, 2004, 271.

the most advantageous route for the canal continued for the next few years. In 1911, the management of the Chamber intervened in this matter among the Polish parliamentarians sitting in the Austrian State Council.⁶¹ In addition, the investor, i.e. the Ministry of Trade, was expected to protect the city against floods which exposed the local industry to irreparable financial losses.⁶² At the same time, despite the emerging concerns, appeals were made to the Austrian authorities to start the construction of the planned investment as soon as possible. Representatives of the Lviv Chamber of Commerce and Industry came to the aid of the efforts of the authorities of the Krakow Chamber.

On November 16, 1912, in Lviv, a meeting was organized in the building of the Diet of Galicia and Lodomeria with the participation of institutions interested in the construction of the Vistula-Dniester canal.⁶³ During the conference, various variants of running the canal were considered, e.g. along the Galician Railway of Archduke Charles Louis (southern variant) and along the Vistula towards Mielec and further near Leżajsk, entering the San valley (northern variant). The Lviv Chamber of Commerce and Industry supported the southern variant of the course of the canal. Ludwik Tenner presented the position of the Chamber, arguing that the proposed canal route would cover 296 kilometres of railway, and the northern variant only 172 kilometres. Therefore, taking into account the economic aspects of construction, the particular interests of individual cities should not be taken into account. Tenner's opinion was convergent with the position of e.g. Józef Bund representing the Krakow Chamber of Commerce and Industry, Józef Tertil - the mayor of Tarnów, and delegates of the Krakow authorities. Ultimately, however, it did not find recognition. After several months of negotiations, in November 1913, the National Department unanimously adopted the northern variant of the navigable canal, passing through the central part of the Sandomierz Basin.⁶⁴ The project

⁶¹ L. Zachuta and A. Zdebski, *Izba Przemysłowo-Handlowa w Krakowie (1850-2000)*, Kraków, 2000, 47–48.

⁶² Regulacja Wisły, Projekt kanału Wisła-Dniestr, AGAD 1/310/0/6/365, 109–114.

⁶³ Kanał Wisła-Dniestr, cz. II, *Kurjer Lwowski* 536, 21 November 1913, 2.

⁶⁴ Kanał Wisła-Dniestr, *Kurjer Lwowski* 533, 20 November 1913, 2.

envisaged that from Radymno on the San the canal would continue east to Sudova Vyshnia, and there, after crossing the watershed between the Baltic Sea and the Black Sea catchment, it would branch out. The main canal was to run to Zhydachiv and get connected with the Dniester, while the side channel was to run towards Lviv. Thus, the investment would be crucial also for Lviv itself, which was to become a port city for inland navigation.⁶⁵ Ingarden believed that such a route of the canal would cause economic revival in the agricultural Sandomierz Basin.⁶⁶ He also proposed a compromise between the northern and southern routes, but it was never considered feasible by politicians. The Vistula-Dniester Canal was also supposed to have an artificial connection with the upper Bug (Vistula basin) and Styr (Dnieper basin). However, detailed design work on this canal was never undertaken.⁶⁷ The investment in the southern variant of the Vistula-Dniester canal was estimated at 300 million kronas. The huge costs resulted from the need to regulate the Dniester, which was not a fully navigable river for larger vessels.

Continuous discussions on the variants of running the canal from the Vistula to the Dniester did not prevent the inauguration of the construction of the Oder-Vistula reach from the border of Galicia and Austrian Silesia to Krakow (Fig. 3B). In December 1911, the cornerstone was laid near Brzeźnica, and in the spring of the following year, construction began on the Zator-Krakow reach.⁶⁸ 1958 was then indicated as the expected year of its completion.⁶⁹ However, in the case of regulating the rivers flowing into the canal, financed from the national budget, work began only with a slight delay, in 1904.⁷⁰

⁶⁵ O. Nadolski, Kanał ślawnny Dunaj-Dniestr, *Przegląd Techniczny* 49, 22 (1911) 286–287.

⁶⁶ R. Ingarden, *Trasa kanału żeglugi Wisła-Dniestr*, Lwów, 1913, 9–12.

⁶⁷ M. Matakiewicz, *Drogi wodne w Polsce*, Lwów, 1917, 37–40.

⁶⁸ Biliński, *Wspomnienia i dokumenty*, 221–222; K. Drewnowski, Rozpoczęcie budowy kanałów w Galicyi, *Czasopismo Techniczne* 1 (1912) 14–15.

⁶⁹ M. Matakiewicz, Memoriał Towarzystwa Politechnicznego we Lwowie o noweli do ustawy o budowie dróg wodnych w Austrii z 11. czerwca 1901 Dz. p. p. Nr. 66, wniesionej przez c. k. Rząd z końcem grudnia 1911 w Izbie posłów pod tytułem: Entwurf eines Gesetzes womit ergänzende, *Czasopismo Techniczne* 10 (1912) 1–14.

⁷⁰ Ingarden, *Rzeki i kanały*.

In its pre-Krakow reach, the Galician Canal had the following dimensions: 30 metres in the width of the water surface and 16 metres in the width of the bottom. The banks of the canal were secured with a rip-rap or a layer of concrete. The bottom of the canal was made of concrete or clay. A towpath was designed on the banks of the canal. Ships were expected to overcome level differences using single locks. All water was to come from the rivers flowing into the canal, which forced their hasty regulation. The flow of water and bedload was to be controlled on the main Carpathian rivers flowing into the canal still before their connections. The canal designed in this way was to make possible the movement of boats weighing not more than 600 tonnes and a draft of up to 1.8 metres. A ship could be up to 67 metres long and 8.2 metres wide.⁷¹

Before the outbreak of World War I, 16 km of the canal was built from Brzeźnica to Samborek (currently a housing estate in the town of Skawina) with the most important facilities, i.e. bridges and siphons enabling the flow of waters of smaller watercourses under the canal bottom. In this way, 48.7% of the cost estimate for the amount of 6,249,300 kronas was met. Also, a several-hundred-metre long reach of the canal flowing into the Vistula in Krakow's Ludwinów was built, meeting 61% of the cost estimate amounting to 2,959,200 kronas. In Krakow, sewers were made on the left bank of the Vistula and boulevard walls on both banks, which were to make possible the later adaptation of the river to navigation by damming it with the help of a weir. The completed structures were already fulfilling their anti-flood function at that time. As part of the municipal works, 90% of the cost estimate for the amount of 12,409,700 kronas was completed. During that period, about 40% of regulatory works were also carried out on the Carpathian tributaries of the Vistula and the Dniester.⁷²

During World War I, work on the construction of the Brzeźnica-Samborek canal was stopped. While Austria focused on defensive operations on the Carpathian front, German

⁷¹ Matakiewicz, *Drogi wodne w Polsce*.

⁷² M. Rybczyński, *Drogi wodne i regulacja rzek, Przegląd Techniczny* 4–5 (1929) 151–157.

engineers worked intensively on the design of connecting the Oder and Vistula rivers in the north, and further on the Dniester River. This waterway was to use the canalised Vistula and San, and then get connected with the Dniester according to the pre-war Galician concept.⁷³

THE FALL OF THE HABSBURG EMPIRE AND THE IDEA OF INTERNATIONAL CHANNELS

The emergence of nation states after the disintegration of the Habsburg Empire was the reason for the lack of interest in building international transport networks. The new independent states where the Danube-Oder-Elbe-Vistula-Dniester canal network was to be located (Austria, Czechoslovakia, and Poland) continued to work on the development of domestic water transport. In Czechoslovakia, it was assumed that inland navigation would take place on natural rivers. Czech nationalists believed that connecting the national shipping network with the Danube would be a return to the economic hegemony of the German-speaking states.⁷⁴

After Poland regained independence, discussions on connecting the Vistula with the Dniester returned. Nevertheless, the project itself met with numerous objections. One of its adversaries was a well-known hydrotechnician, Roman Ingarden, who emphasized that the regulation of the Dniester was unprofitable, and the construction of the waterway was questionable from the point of view of international politics.⁷⁵

Despite the emerging dilemmas and negative opinions of specialists like Ingarden, the authorities of the reborn and independent Poland still tried to launch this river communication route of key importance for the Second Polish Republic, referring directly to the old Austrian plans. This project was primarily aimed at connecting Krakow with the coal basin in Silesia. Despite the strategic importance of the planned investment for socio-economic relations, its

⁷³ P. Ehlers, *Binnenwasserstrassen des Ostens, mit einem Langenschnitt und einer farbigen Karte*, Danzig, 1917.

⁷⁴ J. Janáč and E. van der Vleuten, Transnational system building across geopolitical shifts: The Danube-Oder-Elbe Canal, 1901-2015, *Water Alternatives* 9, 2 (2016) 278–280.

⁷⁵ Ingarden, *Rzeki i kanały*.

construction stretched over time, largely because of the financial difficulties of the young state, which were compounded by macroeconomic problems and the great economic depression. According to Łotysz, the entire project of building waterways in independent Poland was the result of ambitions exceeding possibilities, which often even harmed the interests of the state.⁷⁶

Despite the inclusion of the Galician Canal in the general design of waterways from 1919, its construction was finally abandoned.⁷⁷ Navigation to the north-east of Krakow was to be possible thanks to the canalised Vistula. In 1920, studies were started to make the Vistula more passable from Krakow to the mouth of the San. In 1921, geodetic works began on the route of the future Dąbrowa Górniczo-Spytkowice canal, where it was to get connected with the Brzeźnica-Samborek reach, which was already under construction.⁷⁸ In 1924, a programme of river training was established, which was a continuation of the work undertaken before World War I.⁷⁹ The river training of the Vistula itself was justified not only by the need to facilitate navigation, but also by the possibility of creating new agricultural land.⁸⁰ In the 1920s, however, investments were mainly made in the development of railway transport. In 1925, more than 96% of the communication budget was allocated to railways.⁸¹

In 1926, representatives of the Advisory and Technical Commission for Communication and Transit operating at the League of Nations, established in 1921 to organize matters related to inland navigation in post-war Europe, were hosted in Poland. Representatives of the Commission were to assess the possibility of organizing water transport in Poland on the Coal Canal connecting Gdańsk with Silesia, and the Vistula-Prypiat – east-west connection, involving the drainage of the large-area wetlands in Polesie. In the final report, the experts

⁷⁶ S. Łotysz, Transeuropejska droga wodna przez Polesie a kwestia jego osuszenia w II Rzeczypospolitej, *Kwartalnik Historii Nauki i Techniki* 63, 1 (2018) 7–37.

⁷⁷ T. Tillinger, Sztuczne drogi wodnej, *Roboty Publiczne* 1 (1919) 31.

⁷⁸ Sprawozdanie z działalności Ministerstwa Robót Publicznych VIII 1920 - XII 1921, Central Archives of Modern Records in Warsaw, 2/3/0/5.1/308, 7–8.

⁷⁹ Regulacja Dniestru i Stryja, *Chwila* 1873, 2 June 1924, 6.

⁸⁰ 1000 kilometrów ornej ziemi dla regulacji Wisły, *Chwila* 4235, 9 January 1931, 11.

⁸¹ A. Legun-Biliński, Nasze projekty kanałowe, *Przegląd Techniczny* 46 (1927) 966–970.

advised against the construction of the Coal Canal and recommended focusing efforts and resources on regulating the Vistula and building the Silesia-Krakow canal.⁸²

The budget for 1937 guaranteed funding for the work facilitating navigation on the upper Vistula and the construction of new river ports. This investment was associated with the construction of the Central Industrial District. There were also plans to modernise the old navigable canals in north-eastern Poland, i.e. the Royal, Augustowski, and Ogiński Canals.⁸³ These plans definitely confirm the withdrawal from the construction of the Vistula-Dniester canal and the use of inland navigation mainly for the transport of coal. Despite this, representatives of Eastern Lesser Poland continued to lobby for the Galician Canal.⁸⁴

Irrespective of the government, actions in favour of the waterways were undertaken by social and economic organizations. The most important activities of this type included the establishment in 1938 of the Society for Supporting the Construction of the Coal Basin-Krakow Shipping Canal. The top leadership of the society included, among its other members, Wincenty Hyla – Polish independence activist, and long-term member of the Sejm of the Republic of Poland. The main objectives of the established organization included: promoting information among the population on the importance of the canal for Polish socio-economic relations, submitting social demands regarding the canal to the government and, finally, distributing messages on the actions taken by the state around the planned investment.⁸⁵

In 1937, economic circles from the eastern part of the former Galicia began to work in favour of launching a waterway connecting the Baltic Sea with the Black Sea, through the Vistula, San, Dniester, and Prut. At that time, on the initiative of professor Otto Nadolski,

⁸² Konopka, *Ekspersi Ligi Narodów*, 361.

⁸³ Rewii ministrów – ciąg dalszy, *Chwila* 6425, 7 February 1937, 15; Zagadnienie centralnego okręgu przemysłowego, *Chwila* 6701, 16 November 1937, 11.

⁸⁴ O budowę kanału Wisła-Dniestr. Postulaty inwestycyjne rolnictwa Małopolski Wschodniej, *Chwila* 6457, 11 March 1937, 11.

⁸⁵ Założenie Towarzystwa Popierania Budowy Kanału Żeglugi Zagłębie Węglowe-Kraków, State Archives in Katowice, Branch in Bielsko-Biała, 13/360/1300, 1–5, 7–8, 11.

president of the Polish Polytechnic Society in Lviv, the Baltic-Black Sea Waterway Committee, which worked primarily to reach an agreement with the Romanian side regarding the inclusion of the Prut River in the waterway, was founded. This project assumed the use of the route of the original design of the Galician Canal only on the San-Dniester reach.⁸⁶

Also in 1937, a brochure promoting the construction of waterways as an educational measure was published. Its author postulated the possibility of employing up to 60,000 prisoners at the construction of the canal.⁸⁷ These predictions were not unjustified, as already in the summer of 1937, 5,500 prisoners worked on the regulation of the Vistula River.⁸⁸

Despite the changes in the waterways policy, works on the canal from Brzeźnica to Samborek and in Krakow's Ludwinów were carried out until the outbreak of World War II. In the years 1929-1937, however, only maintenance works were carried out for economic reasons.⁸⁹ In 1937, the construction was resumed, justified by the increase in the prices of rail and road transport, and consequently, the improvement in the profitability of water transport.⁹⁰ The construction of the canal was interrupted by the outbreak of World War II. Despite the abandonment of the construction of the canal by the Nazi occupier, in 1942, the Polish Construction Service, established in the General Government, completed the construction of the port in Krakow's district of Płaszów.⁹¹ However, it was much smaller than the facility designed before World War I.

The reach of the Brzeźnica-Samborek canal, built before World War II, was adapted in the 1950s as an approach flume for the heat and power plant in Skawina, definitively ending the more than fifty-year history of the construction of the shipping canal. This reach is part of

⁸⁶ Konopka, *Eksperci Ligi Narodów*.

⁸⁷ Polsce potrzebna jest dobra sieć dróg wodnych! *Chwila* 818, 24 April 1937, 9.

⁸⁸ Zbiorowy akt łaski P. Prezydenta Rzplitej. 144 więźniów kryminalnych uzyskuje wolność, *Chwila* 6834, 30 March 1938, 1.

⁸⁹ Kędzior, *Roboty wodne i melioracyjne w Południowej Małopolsce*; M. Rybczyński, *Drogi wodne i regulacja rzek*.

⁹⁰ J. Flach, *Kamienny skarb, Światowid* 34 (1938) 2.

⁹¹ Od wiosny do jesieni trwa praca Polskiej Służby Budowlanej, *Gazeta Lwowska* 72, 26 March 1942, 3.

the Upper Vistula Waterway, the length of which (16 km), its parameters and isolation from other ways do not make the organization of profitable inland navigation possible.

The infrastructural effects of the implementation of the Galician Canal project are still visible in the valleys of the Carpathian rivers, even hundreds of kilometres away from the constructed reach of the canal. The regulation of the Carpathian rivers was an essential element of the construction of the shipping canal. It was carried out to control the flow of water and bedload transport on the rivers that were to feed the future canal. Hydrotechnical work was also done to make mountain channels passable and thus to facilitate the rafting of goods. This work was also beneficial from the point of view of flood risk management. The regulation of the Carpathian rivers is particularly controversial in retrospect owing to the final abandonment of the construction of the Galician Canal. In the interwar period, when the fate of water transport in Poland was in the balance, the Carpathian rivers were consistently regulated in accordance with the guidelines for rivers that were to supply the shipping canal. At the beginning of the Nazi occupation of Poland, the process of comprehensive river training, which irretrievably destroyed the natural environment of the Carpathian river valleys, was completed. It was proved that the regulation of the Carpathian rivers carried out as part of the Galician Canal project initiated the process of channel bed erosion, described many times in the scientific literature, leading to the lowering of the Carpathian river beds by up to 3 metres.⁹²

The Carpathian rivers, in accordance with the guidelines, were narrowed to about 30 metres in width and their new, artificial banks were secured with rip-rap. Fragments of channels abandoned in this way were planted with willow in order to force the sedimentation of silt and to fill these areas.⁹³ This work led to the creation of winding or even straight channel patterns. This method is widely used and is not controversial owing to the use of natural materials. The

⁹² K. Witkowski, The Galician Canal – An unrealized project that changed the rivers in the northern part of the Carpathians, *River Research and Applications* 37, 9 (2021) 1343–1356.

⁹³ M. Matakiewicz, *Regulacja rzek*, Lwów-Kraków-Warszawa, 1921.

problem with the regulation of the Carpathian rivers at that time lies in the channel pattern of the channels, which were subjected to hydrotechnical treatments. The natural Carpathian channels, which existed until the beginning of the twentieth century, had a braiding or anabranching reaches. Thus, complex channel patterns with numerous islands and bars functioned in the bottoms of the valleys, which were rapidly transformed into maximally simplified single-thread patterns. The scale of this practice is well illustrated by the example of the River Skawa near Zator, where a natural anabranching channel with a width of more than 900 metres was replaced by a channel with a width of 30 metres. During the work, 889.5 km of channels out of 2,317 km of the total river length were regulated, which accounted for 38.4% of the rivers listed in the Act. Only in the case of the Dunajec, as much as 55% of the reaches indicated for regulation were the multiple-channels.

As a result of hydrotechnical work, not only the channel patterns of the main Carpathian rivers were simplified. According to the Act of the Diet of Galicia and Lodomeria of May 9, 1907, the highest lying mountain streams in the mountains were also to be regulated.⁹⁴ This work, in most cases, started only in the interwar period and consisted in building up mountain channels with concrete or stone dams. Many of these hydrotechnical facilities have survived to this day.

River training carried out in connection with the construction of the Galician Canal drastically changed the conditions in the bottoms of the Carpathian river valleys. The artificial limitation of the floodplains and the incision of the channels resulted in the creation of fluvial anthropospheres along rivers, in which the river had to adapt its flow to artificial conditions. These are areas where anthropopressure modifies natural processes, causing instability and, as a result, increasing the threat to humans. Such effects of regulation have been described many times in the geomorphological literature, however, the case of the Carpathian rivers is unique

⁹⁴ Journal of National Laws, No. 60, 1907.

owing to the fact that the reason for the regulation, i.e. the Galician Canal, has not been implemented.⁹⁵

CONCLUSIONS

The construction of the Oder-Vistula-Dniester Canal, also known as the Galician Canal, was started for political reasons. Kozińska-Witt even believes that the actual purpose of the 1901 Act was to silence national conflicts in the Empire.⁹⁶ Numerous voices for the construction of a network of navigable canals in the Habsburg Empire and, equally, numerous against it, did not favour making decisions based solely on economic calculations. The vision of navigable canals must also have seemed so vague to the then potential investors that it was only in the 1930s that discussions began about the involvement of private capital.⁹⁷ However, this resistance to investing in water management was not widespread in the Empire, as evidenced by the huge involvement of private investors in the regulation of the Hungarian Tisza River.⁹⁸ However, in retrospect, this project was assessed as economically unjustified and harmful to the environment.

The lack of significant progress in the work on the canal before 1918 can be explained by the reluctance of the central authorities to invest in peripheral Galicia. However, in the times of the Second Polish Republic, which was the heir of Galician investments, the failure of large shipping and drainage projects was the result of the lack of a coherent and long-term government policy in the field of water management, as is confirmed by the research of Łotysz. East-west waterways were also considered strategically dangerous at the time because they

⁹⁵ A. Gurnell, N. Surian and L. Zanoni, Multi-thread river channels: A perspective on changing European alpine river systems, *Aquatic Sciences* 71, 3 (2009) 253–265.

⁹⁶ Kozińska-Witt, '[...] gdy stary Wawel otoczą wody kanału', 360.

⁹⁷ Łotysz, Transeuropejska droga wodna.

⁹⁸ Z. Pinke, Modernization and decline: an eco-historical perspective on regulation of the Tisza Valley, Hungary, *Journal of Historical Geography* 45 (2014) 92–105.

connected Germany with Russia. Railways also constituted an increasing competition for water transport in Poland and Europe.⁹⁹

The construction of the Galician Canal, or an equivalent water connection, was considered for nearly forty years, from the adoption of the Imperial Act in 1901 to the outbreak of World War II. Throughout that whole period, representatives of the Chambers of Commerce and Industry from Kraków and Lviv, as well as local government politicians, should be considered the greatest advocates of the new waterway. In the case of politicians of the Imperial Council in Vienna, and later the Sejm of the Second Polish Republic, the position on the construction of waterways was not so clear. Also among the inhabitants of Galicia there was enthusiasm for the new investment, which it was hoped would cause the economic revival of the region. Voices of opposition to the construction of the canal among local residents began to be heard only at the stage of detailed design. However, these were usually voices calling for a change in the route of the canal, and not abandoning its construction altogether. However, this problem affected only a small group of the Galicians who lived along the already built Brzeźnica-Samborek reach.

The legacy of the Galician Canal is not only the short reach of the canal with a length of 16 km, but also the boulevards and the first sewage collectors in Krakow. The Vistula hydrotechnical structures in Krakow were planned already before 1901.¹⁰⁰ However, the construction of the canal accelerated this work and made it possible to finance them. The course of the existing boulevards was forced by the design of the shipping canal, which was to get connected with the Vistula at the mouth of the Wilga – this reach was completed in the 1930s. Although the location of the main port of Krakow was not finally decided on, the western part of the boulevards was designed as the quay of the winter port. Owing to the interruption of the

⁹⁹ Łotysz, *Transeuropejska droga wodna*; Marti-Henneberg, *European integration and national models for railway networks*.

¹⁰⁰ Purchla, *Kraków – prowincja czy metropolia*.

construction of the Galician Canal, the reach of the quay in Krakow, which was treated as a structure accompanying the canal, eventually became the main and very unfavourable route of inland navigation, with a bend with an angle of over ninety degrees. Despite the fact that the canal was not completed, the work related to its construction reduced the flood risk in Krakow and supported the idea of building 'Great Krakow'.¹⁰¹

The impact of the Galician Canal reached the furthest in the case of the regulation of the Carpathian rivers. Certainly, as a result of the floods in the 1930s and 1940s, many of the reaches regulated during the construction of the canal underwent self-renaturalisation. However, the channel incision process initiated at that time has continued to this day. These processes, which were unfavourable from the human point of view, were the result of a chain reaction, which was initiated by the first channel regulation related to the construction of the canal. The artificial narrowing of the channel created the illusion of security and led people to farm in areas that only a few years earlier had been part of the channels. This, in turn, forced the authorities to embank the rivers and hastily repair the reaches of regulation that had been damaged by the flood.¹⁰² It should be expected that if it had not been for the great river training action launched in connection with the construction of the Vistula-Dniester canal, the Carpathian rivers would not have been regulated on a large scale. After World War II, no repair work was carried out in the Dniester basin, as there was in the Vistula basin, resulting in many river reaches regaining their natural character, e.g. the River Stryi anabranching channel in the town of Stryi. This condition has lasted to this day and provides people with greater protection against floods than artificial structures, not adapted to natural conditions.

The braiding and anabranching reaches of the Vistula's tributaries, which functioned in natural conditions at the beginning of the twentieth century and were regulated for the first time

¹⁰¹ Kozińska-Witt, '[...] gdy stary Wawel otoczą wody kanału'.

¹⁰² K. Witkowski, Man's impact on the transformation of channel patterns (the Skawa River, southern Poland), *River Research and Applications* 37 (2021) 150–162.

as part of the work related to the construction of the Vistula-Dniester canal, will never be fully renaturalised. Contemporary hydrometeorological conditions in the Vistula basin and land use still favour the functioning of wide multiple-channel systems. This is confirmed by floods, which cause the local destruction of regulatory structures and significant widening of the channel combined with the emergence of islands and bars.¹⁰³ Unfortunately, owing to the significant incision of the Carpathian river channels and, above all, the development of the former areas of the channels, it is not possible to restore the natural conditions. According to Wohl, these irretrievably changed reaches of valleys are the legacies of the first destructive anthropopressure.¹⁰⁴ The infrastructural legacy of the Habsburg Empire is, therefore, visible not only in the structures that have survived to this day, but also in the permanently changed natural environment.

¹⁰³ E. Gorczyca, K. Krzemiń, K. Jarzyna, The Evolution of Gravel-Bed Rivers during the Post-Regulation Period in the Polish Carpathians, *Water* 12 (2020) 254.

¹⁰⁴ Wohl, *Forgotten legacies*.

Fig. 1. Map of the waterways of the Habsburg Empire in 1895.

Numbers of waterways in accordance with the entries in table 1.

Source: own elaboration based on: Map Die Schifffahrtsstrassen in Österreich-Ungarn in: *Brockhaus' Konversations-Lexikon, edition 14, reprint 3, volume 12 Moria-Pes*, Leipzig, Berlin, Vienna, 1903, 716-717.

Fig. 2. The most important goods floated down the Vistula and its tributaries in the years 1878-1910, and the number of rafts and scows used for transport.

Fig. 3. A. Designed shipping canals in the northern part of the Empire. B. Detailed design of the reach of the Oder-Vistula canal.

1 – river, 2 – canal intended to use steamboat, 3 – river intended to use steamboat, 4 – river intended to use rowboat, 5 – floatable river listed in the 1901 Act, 6 – designed canal listed in the 1901 Act, 7 – southern variant of the Vistula-Dniester canal, 8 – section of the Oder-Vistula canal designed in detail, 9 – canal sections built in 1911-1958 (Laczany Canal), 10 – city, 11 – border of the Habsburg Empire.

Tab. 1. Waterways of the Habsburg Empire in 1895.

Numbers of waterways in accordance with the figure 1.

Source: own elaboration based on: Map Die Schifffahrtsstrassen in Österreich-Ungarn in: *Brockhaus' Konversations-Lexikon, edition 14, reprint 3, volume 12 Moria-Pes*, Leipzig, Berlin, Vienna, 1903, 716-717.

Preprint

Preprint

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basin	number	watercourse	from (upstream)	to (downstream)	length of watercourse [km]		intended to use [km]		crone land
					canal	river	row boat	steam boat	
Black Sea	1	* Danube	German border	Devin	-	346.27	-	346.27	UA, LA
	1a		Devin	Orşova	-	960.5	-	960.5	HU
	2	- Inn	German border	Inn mouth	-	65.77	65.77	-	UA
	2a		Hall in Tirol	German border	-	82.73	82.73	-	CT
	3	-- Salzach	Hallein	Salzach mouth	-	80.58	80.58	-	SUA
	4	- Traun	Lake Traun	Traun mouth	-	74.58	74.58	-	UA
	5	-- Lake Traun (Traunsee)			-	11.8	-	11.8	UA
	6	- Enns	Steyr	Enns mouth	-	31.22	31.22	-	UA, LA
	6a		Hieflau	Altenmarkt bei Sant Gallen	-	25.3	25.3	-	DS
	7	- Donaukanal	Danube river	Danube river	16.66	-	-	16.66	LA
	8	- Morava	Hodonin	Morawa mouth	-	119.14	119.14	-	MM, LA
	9	- Moson Danube (right branch of Danube)	Danube river	Danube river	-	15.9	-	15.9	HU
	10	- Little Danube (left branch of Danube)	Danube river	Danube river	-	13.6	13.6	-	HU
	11	- Wag	Vazsec	Wag mouth	-	317.52	317.52	-	HU
	12	-- Nitra	Nazsvad	Nitra mouth	-	15.12	15.2	-	HU
	13	- Hron	Podbrezova	Hron mouth	-	146.64	146.64	-	HU
	14	- Szentendre Danube (right branch of Danube)	Danube river	Danube river	-	30.3	30.3	-	HU
	15	- Sio	Ádánd	Sio mouth		143.51	143.51	-	HU
	16	-- Sio Canal	Lake Balaton	Ádánd	12	-	12	-	HU
	17	--- Lake Balaton			-	121	-	121	HU
	18	- left branch of Danube in Mohacs	Danube river	Danube river	-	56	-	56	HU
	19	- Great Bačka Canal (Franzenskanal)	Danube river	Tisza river	238.2	-	3.2	235	HU
	20	-- Little Bačka Canal (Josephkanal)	Great Bačka Canal	Danube river					HU
	21	- Drava	Mur mouth	Drava mouth	-	248.82	19.82	229	HU
21a		Maribor	Središče ob Dravi	-	55.91	55.91	-	DS, KD	
21b		Villach	Wolbl	-	126.3	126.3	-	DC	
22	-- Mur	Bad Radkersburg	Racz-Kanizsa	-	32.66	32.66	-	DS	
23	-- Wörthersee			-	16	-	16	DC	
24	--- Lendkanal	Klagenfurt	Wörthersee	4.1	-	4.1	-	DC	

	25	- Tisza	Tisza Ujlak	Tisza mouth	-	969.49	508.4	461.09	HU
	26	- Begakanal	Bega river	Bega mouth	115	-	-	115	HU
	27	- Mureş	Ocna Mureş	Mureş mouth	-	367.92	249.92	118	HU
	28	- Körös	Bekes	Körös mouth	-	219.23	92.23	127	HU
	29	- Bodrog	Sáros-patak	Bodrog mouth	-	30.34	30.34	-	HU
	30	- Someş	Satu Mare	Someş mouth	-	98.61	98.61	-	HU
	31	- Sava	Kupa mouth	Sava mouth	-	663.5	59.5	604	HU
	31a		Zidani Most	Bregan	-	60.39	60.39	-	CAR
	32	-- Bosut	Vinkovci	Bosut mouth	-	49	-	49	HU
	33	-- Kupa	Karlovac	Kupa mouth	-	135.79	135.79	-	HU
	34	-- Ljubljana	Vrhnik	Ljubljana	-	22.76	22.76	-	CAR
	35	- Timiş	Pancevo	Timiş mouth	-	3	-	3	HU
	36	* Dniester	Stryj mouth	Russian border	-	376.5	376.5	-	KGL
Baltic Sea	37	* Oder	Opawa	Nowy Dwór	-	27.05	27.05	-	ULS
	38	* Vistula	Przemsza mouth	Zawichost	-	298.8	-	298.8	KGL
	39	- Przemsza	German border	Przemsza mouth	-	23.4	-	23.4	KGL
	40	- Dunajec	Biała mouth	Dunajec mouth	-	30.8	30.8	-	KGL
	41	- San	Krzeszow	San mouth	-	58	-	58	KGL
	42	- Bug	Sokal	Russian border	-	31.5	31.5	-	KGL
North Sea	43	* Rhine	Rheineck	Lake Constance	-	5.1	-	5.1	V
	43a		Liechtenstein border	Rheineck	-	39.9	39.9	-	V
	44	* Elbe	Melnik	German border	-	110.3	-	110.3	KB
	45	- Vltava	Štěchovice	Vltava mouth	-	83.74	-	83.74	KB
	45a		Malše mouth	Štěchovice	-	162	162	-	KB
Adriatic Sea	46	* Adige	Bronzolo	Italy border	-	99.86	99.86	-	AL
	47	* Ausa	Cervignano	Portobuso	-	21.32	-	21.32	AL
	48	* Natissa	Panigai	Natissa mouth	-	8.8	-	8.8	AL
	48a		Aquileia	Panigai	-	4.9	4.9	-	AL
	49	- Terzo	Terzo	Terzo mouth	-	4	4	-	AL
	50	- Canale Anfora	Terzo river	Ausa river	11.1	-	-	11.1	AL
	51	channels within the Marano Lagoon			31.6	0	5.5	26.1	AL
	52	* Isonzo	Morosini	Isonzo mouth	-	9.81	9.81	-	AL
	53	* Timavo	Monfalcone	Timavo mouth	-	2.59	-	2.59	AL
	54	* Dragonja	Dragonja	Dragonja mouth	-	4.7	4.7	-	AL
	55	* Mirna	Motovun	Mirna mouth	-	19.85	19.85	-	AL
	56	* Zrmanja	Obrovac	Zrmanja mouth	-	10.81	-	10.81	KD
	57	* Krka	Skradinski Buk	Krka mouth	-	13.89	-	13.89	KD
	58	* Cetina	Podaspilje	Cetina mouth	-	6.5	6.5	-	KD
59	* Neretva	Metkovic	Neretva mouth	-	20.47	-	20.47	KD	
60	* Ombla (gulf, river)	Komolac	Ombla mouth	-	3.79	-	3.79	KD	

* main river, - tributary of the main river, --, --- subsequent tributary

crone lands: UA - Upper Austria, LA - Lower Austria, HU - Arch-Kingdom of Hungary, CT - Princely County of Tyrol, SUA - Duchy of Salzburg and Upper Austria, DS - Duchy of Styria, MM - Margraviate of Moravia, DC - Duchy of Carinthia, CAR - Duchy of Carniola, KGL - Kingdom of Galicia and Lodomeria, with the Grand Duchy of Kraków and the Duchies of Auschwitz and Zator, ULS - Duchy of Upper and Lower Silesia, V - Vorarlberg, KB - Kingdom of Bohemia, AL - Austrian Littoral, KD - Kingdom of Dalmatia

Source: own elaboration based on: Map Die Schifffahrtsstrassen in Österreich-Ungarn in: Brockhaus' Konversations-Lexikon, edition 14, reprint 3, volume 12 Moria-Pes, Leipzig, Berlin, Vienna, 1903, 716-717.